

BIOINSPIRED MICROVASCULAR NETWORKS FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Bioinspired, Fiber-reinforced composite, Microvascular, Multifunctional

ABSTRACT

In biological systems, fluid transport through internal vasculature enables a plurality of metabolic and homeostatic functions including respiration, circulation, thermal regulation, and self-repair. Natural, load-bearing materials such as bone and wood rely on nutrient exchange through a series of complex networks to achieve mechanical stasis via cellular proliferation (growth) and tissue regeneration. While synthetic fiber-reinforced composites (FRC) attain comparable specific strength/stiffness properties to these living hierarchical materials, the ability to sustain structural performance over a wide range of environmental conditions and engineering applications has yet to be accomplished. One promising pathway for accession of multifunctionality in man-made FRC is to mimic successful, evolutionary-derived vascular constructions.

Here we show advancements for a recently developed technique [1-3] designated vaporization of sacrificial components (VaSC), where inverse replica microvasculature is created within fiber-composites through thermal depolymerization of a sacrificial precursor. Metal catalyst micro-particles are incorporated into a commodity biopolymer, poly(lactic) acid (PLA), and extruded into printable filament for an additive manufacturing process known as fused deposition modeling (FDM). The sacrificial printing technique is both economical and scalable using commercially available materials, processes, and equipment. By expanding the VaSC procedure beyond one-dimensional (1D) segregated channels, to three-dimensional (3D) interconnected networks closer resembling biological vasculature, the range of dynamic functionalities for fiber-composites is increased. In addition to providing enhanced multifunctional properties, 3D printed networks also possess damage-tolerant features found in natural vasculatures [4].

1 INTRODUCTION

Extensive vasculature in natural composites, such as osteonic canals in bone and vessel elements in wood imbue these lightweight structural materials with capabilities for fluidic mass and energy transport. Typical man-made fiber-composites possess comparable structural characteristics but lack the dynamic functionality of their natural counterparts. Various research groups have constructed microchannels within FRC for self-healing and sensing applications [5-17], however these were

primarily restricted to 1D, linear conduits by the available manufacturing processes. A requisite for creating more damage tolerant fluidics, e.g. those mimetic of 3D hierarchical vasculature in natural systems [4], is the ability to fabricate branched and interconnected microvascular networks.

Figure 1 illustrates the effect of restricted fluid distribution after arterial puncture in the primitive, dichotomous venation of a *Ginkgo biloba* leaf (Figure 1a), compared to nutrient rerouting in the later evolved, branched vasculature of *Citrus limon* (Figure 1b). An incessant microvascular manufacturing challenge has been to recreate complex, biomimetic architectures with “sacrificial” precursors that can also survive structural host material integration requirements. Prior developed direct-write assembly [18, 19] of wax-based fugitive inks produces intricate, 3D interconnected vascular templates that can be incorporated into solid polymer systems via liquid monomer infusion [20-23]. These sacrificial scaffolds however, are too delicate to survive fiber-reinforced composites (FRC) processing under elevated temperatures and/or compaction pressure. The VaSC process [1-3] with catalyst (SnOx) infused thermoplastic PLA, has proven to be an efficient method for creating microvascular networks throughout a FRC. Segregated, undulating sacrificial PLA fibers have been co-woven into a non-crimp orthogonal [24] reinforcement textile and evacuated post-composite fabrication to yield micro channels capable of imparting multifunctional properties, e.g. active cooling, electromagnetic-modulation [1]. Three-dimensional, interpenetrating vasculature to improve *in situ* mixing of liquid healing agents has been constructed in FRC laminates [2] via interwoven sacrificial PLA fibers. However, the resulting 3D microchannels in both cases lack spatial interconnectivity and thus limit fluidic pathway redundancy, i.e. damage tolerance.

This paper describes material processing advancements and resulting versatility of sacrificial PLA achieved through thermal processing of fibers for automated/hand-weaving in composite textile reinforcement, and printable filaments for fused-deposition modeling (FDM) of branched interconnects. Chemical and mechanical tuning achieves targeted vascular objectives of seamless integration, processing survival, and consistent *in situ* evacuation from fiber-reinforced composites. The newfound capabilities in microvascular architecture are demonstrated through fabrication of a state-of-the-art FRC prototype.

Figure 1: Vascular networks in leaves: (a) Fluorescent fluid flow (yellow-green) obstructed by central damage (red) in primitive, dichotomous venation of *Ginkgo biloba*; (b) Redirection of fluid in damage-tolerant, hierarchical branched vasculature of *Citrus limon*. Figure adapted from Katifori et al. [4].

2 SACRIFICIAL POLY-LACTIC ACID (PLA) MATERIALS

Sacrificial PLA was created by combining commercial PLA (4043D, Natureworks LLC) with varying concentrations of tin (II) oxalate (SnOx) catalyst. Both solution and melt-blending [25] techniques were explored to produce a uniform dispersion of catalyst within PLA for improved evacuation (VaSC) characteristics. Since the sacrificial PLA/SnOx material is used to create vascular precursors with features on the microscale (typically between 100-500 μm), the as received SnOx (Sigma-Aldrich) particulates are either sieved or further ground in a high-speed rotary mixer to ensure diameters less than 25 μm .

The depolymerization characteristics of solvent and melt-blended PLA was characterized by isothermal thermogravimetric analysis (iTGA) at 200 °C for 16 h, and compared to neat PLA and prior solvent-swelled sacrificial fibers [1]. Representative iTGA traces (Figure 2) show that neat PLA exhibits less than a 5% weight loss over the 16 h time interval, whereas both solvent-blended and solvent-swelled sacrificial fibers reach a plateau residual mass, equivalent to the original amount of catalyst incorporated, indicating that complete depolymerization (i.e., evacuation) of the PLA has occurred. As SnOx catalyst concentration increases (1, 3, 5, 10%) the time to achieve PLA evacuation decreases (~ 15, 12, 9, 6h), respectively. Thus a trade-off exists between PLA evacuation time and evacuation effectiveness, for which the latter becomes especially important for *in situ* removal when embedded in a structural polymer/composite matrix. The prior solvent-swelled fibers show the greatest proportion of residual catalyst, later confirmed to be surface agglomerations. Producing a uniform distribution of SnOx catalyst throughout the PLA is essential to evacuation consistency.[†]

Figure 2: Isothermal thermogravimetric analysis (iTGA) of various SnOx/PLA combinations at 200 °C for 16 h. [*Note: % values in solvent/melt-blend designate proportion of SnOx by weight of PLA].

3 MELT EXTRUSION OF SACRIFICIAL PLA FIBERS AND FILAMENTS

3.1 Fiber Spinning

In-house sacrificial fibers (550-850 μm diameter) were produced using a modified lab-scale, melt-spinning apparatus (extruder). Sacrificial polymer pieces/pellets (30 g) were loaded into a steel barrel and allowed to melt for 45 minutes at 175 °C. Next, a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) disk followed by brass capped steel piston were inserted into the top barrel opening and mechanically advanced to extrude SnOx/PLA material through a 1.25 mm diameter spinneret at a rate of approximately 5.5 g/min. The extruded fiber was guided over a metal pulley and laterally translated to provide uniform spooling around the winding reel. Rotational speed of the 88 mm diameter take-up reel was adjusted to control fiber size, i.e. faster winding results in diameter reduction for a given extrusion rate. At a winding rate of 41 RPM a single, 30 g extrusion run produced roughly 60 m of continuous 650 μm diameter fiber (Table 1).

[†]3 and 5 % SnOx (by wt. PLA) were typical proportions to achieve consistent *in situ* VaSC.

Wind Rate (RPM)	Fiber Diameter (μm)	Total Length (m)
25	$850 \pm 20^\dagger$	36
33	750 ± 20	48
41	650 ± 20	60

[†]Error represents standard deviation from measurements taken every 5 meters along length.

Table 1: Typical sacrificial, melt-spun fiber size and quantity produced per 30 g batch.

3.2 Filament Extrusion

Larger filament feedstock (~ 3 mm diameter) for fused deposition modeling (FDM) was produced using the same melt-spinning apparatus (at 175 °C) by extruding sacrificial polymer through a brass spinneret extension (75 mm long, 2.5 mm inner-diameter) into a room temperature (RT) water column roughly 1.2 meters tall. Resulting filaments ranged from 2.4 mm to 3.1 mm in diameter, within printable tolerances for the FDM equipment (Section 5).

4 HEATED FIBER DRAWING TO IMPROVE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Post-spinning, heated fiber-drawing (axial stretching) of PLA above the glass-transition temperature ($T_g \sim 57$ °C) and below melting ($T_m \sim 160$ °C) improves mechanical properties, for a given molar mass, due to increased orientation (crystallinity) of polymer chains [25-26]. Initial drawing studies were conducted on short segments of melt-spun fiber (~ 15 cm) that were stretched (drawn) to a length ratio of 3:1 (final/initial) in a heated oven (80 °C) by vertically suspending a mass equivalent to one-fourth the undrawn yield stress (~ 10 MPa). Mechanical properties were assessed by single-fiber tension testing [27] to determine relevant parameters for scale-up.

To produce longer, continuous lengths of drawn fibers, an automated (proprietary) drawing machine (based on the oven-drawn thermal/mechanical guidelines) was developed with collaborators at CU Aerospace, LLC. Draw length ratios ranging between 2:1 - 5:1 were achievable. Post-drawn fibers, produced by either technique, exhibited less variation in diameter and had sufficient strength/ductility to integrate within a reinforcing textile preform (Section 6).

5 FUSED DEPOSITION MODELING (FDM) OF BIOINSPIRED NETWORKS

Fused deposition modeling (FDM) [28, 29] is an emergent, additive manufacturing (rapid-prototyping) technology for creating three-dimensional structures by depositing repeating layers of solidifying melted material. The dispensing apparatus/stage is commonly controlled via computer hardware that is interfaced through computer-aided design (CAD) software. In the FDM described below, sacrificial PLA/SnOx is thermally extruded (printed) onto a heated stage and allowed to cool/solidify, resulting in robust network precursors that survive fiber-reinforced composites manufacturing.

Branched, planar network templates were printed (Figure 3) using a desktop FDM (AO-100, Lulzbot). A solid model of the geometry was created via CAD (SolidWorks v.2011, Dassault Systèmes) and converted to stereolithography (STL) data format. The STL file was then converted to instructional G-code using open source software (Slic3r v.0.9.10b). The G-code was manually edited to further optimize printing pathways. Printing was conducted in two thickness (z) layers with a nozzle diameter of 0.35 mm, a nozzle temperature between 180 - 185 °C, and a bed (stage) temperature between 85 - 90 °C. The printer stage was covered with polyethylene terephthalate (PET) tape and roughened with light sanding (320 grit) to enhance surface adhesion of the printed material. A double network template deposition, including initial calibration border took approximately 1 minute to complete. The bed temperature was lowered to 40 °C ($< T_g$) before removing the sacrificial templates and a final trim of any stray PLA fibrils.

Figure 3: Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) setup: 3D printer (AO-100, Lulzbot) interfaced with desktop computer (Optiplex 790, Dell Inc.), where example network created in 3D solid modeling (CAD) software (Solidworks v.2011, Dassault Systèmes) is displayed on the LCD monitor.

6 EXAMPLE APPLICATION OF PRINTED SACRIFICIAL TEMPLATES: 3D-INTERCONNECTED, BRANCHED NETWORK IN A COMPOSITE LAMINATE

An interconnected microvascular network, intended to sustain fluid delivery in the presence of damage, was constructed by joining sacrificial melt-spun fibers with FDM (printed) branched templates. A 2D woven, glass-fiber composite preform (8H satin, $[90/0]_4$) was prepared by hand stitching melt-spun/post-drawn sacrificial PLA fibers (300 μm) in a parallel configuration while concurrently restraining two branched network precursors on the outer surface. The through-thickness sacrificial fibers and planar network precursors were then chemically bonded by solvent-welding the points of contact via manual injection of a solution of PLA/SnOx (5% by wt.) dissolved in dichloromethane. After air-drying at RT for least 48 h, 4 layers of 8H satin fabric were placed on both top and bottom of the stitched preform and then consolidated into a composite laminate via VARTM (Figure 4a). The final thermal PLA evacuation (VaSC) step produced the first 3D branched, microvascular composite laminate. By filling the empty composite vasculature with a liquid, radiocontrast agent (Iohexol/OmnipaqueTM 350) followed by X-ray computed microtomography, the interconnected network of microchannels is visualized (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Branched vascular construction in a fiber-reinforced composite: (a) *Pre-VaSC* overhead optical image showing printed network templates connected to interwoven sacrificial fibers in a glass-composite laminate (scale bar = 10 mm); (b) *Post-VaSC* X-ray computed microtomography (μCT) of resulting 3D, interconnected vasculature after being filled with a liquid radiocontrast agent (scale bar = 5 mm).

7 CONCLUSIONS

By uniformly dispersing and appropriately sizing SnOx catalyst particles within PLA, a variety of thermal processing techniques for sacrificial microvascular templates have been developed [30]. Melt-spun fibers tailored for strength and ductility in order to weave into fiber-composite preforms are achieved via heated drawing. Production of filament feedstock for rapid-prototyping technologies, i.e. FDM, allows the construction of biomimetic, branched and interconnected vascular precursors. The patterned thermoplastic templates are robust enough to survive and maintain form factor during conventional FRC manufacturing. This series of SnOx/PLA fabrication developments opens the door to an array of envisioned, damage tolerant vascular geometries not only for self-healing, but multifunctional applications including thermal management and electromagnetic reconfigurability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been financially supported by the AFOSR (grant # FA9550-10-1-0255). The authors extend their gratitude to Dr. Leilei Yin of the Beckman Institute's ITG microscopy suite for assistance with micro-CT imaging, and Dr. Chris Mangun of CU Aerospace, LLC for development and commercialization efforts of sacrificial PLA/SnOx under the product name VascTech.

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